

Effect of International Maritime Trade on Cargo Throughputs of Ports in Nigeria (1990-2023)

Onyuku, Kelvin Stella^{1*} & Nwokah. N. Gladson²

¹Department of Maritime Science, Faculty of Science, Rivers State University, Nkpolu-Oroworukwo, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

²Department of Logistics and Supply Chain Management, Faculty of Science, Rivers State University, Nkpolu-Oroworukwo, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

* Corresponding Author: Onyuku, Kelvin Stella, Email: onyuku.kelvin@rsu.edu.ng

APA citation: Onyuku, K.S., & Nwokah, N.G. (2025). Effect of International Maritime Trade on Cargo Throughputs of Ports in Nigeria (1990-2023). *JENER Journal of Empirical and Non-Empirical Research*, 5(3), 177-186

ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 21 Oct 2025</p> <p>Keywords: International Maritime Trade Dry Bulk Cargo Liquid Bulk Cargo Containerized Cargo Cargo Throughputs</p>	<p>This study examined the effect of international maritime trade on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria (1990-2023). The predictor variable (international maritime trade) had its dimensions as dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo and containerized cargo. The criterion variable (cargo throughput) was measured with cargo throughput. The theories that underpinned the study included: Absolute advantage theory, neoclassical theory of external trade, comparative advantage theory and theory of international trade, ex-post facto research design was used for the study. Secondary sources of data were used as the main data collection method. Relevant data for this study were collected from the annual reports and accounts of Nigerian Ports Authority, National Bureau of Statistics and Central Bank of Nigeria Annual Statistical Bulletins (1990 – 2023). The study used descriptive and inferential statistical tools to analyse the data. Specifically, multiple regression analysis of ordinary least square estimation was used to test the hypotheses with the aid of Eviews 12.0. The study adopted ex-post facto research design. The study revealed that there are opportunities to develop and use dry bulk cargo for international maritime trade through ports. That ports provide the platform through which international maritime trade of liquid bulk trade orientation is facilitated and performed. The study found that. ports usually optimize and prioritize containerized trade activities as ways of conducting international maritime trade that help to achieve port performance objectives. That ports provide avenues for the use of containerized trade to smoothen international maritime trade that leads to effective seaport performance. The study found that liquid bulk cargo offers veritable opportunities to optimize international maritime trade distinctions in ports by helping to convert resources, build traffic intensity in trade and engage customers and stakeholders to utilize ports for their international business transactions. The study concluded that: Dry bulk trade has negative and insignificant effect on cargo throughputs ($t = -0.878$); liquid bulk trade has positive and significant effect on cargo throughputs ($t = 4.424$); containerized trade has positive and insignificant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria ($t = 1.355$). This study, therefore, recommended that: Nigerian ports should prioritize and utilize the full capacity available in maritime trade and articulate on dry and liquid bulk cargo handling to improve the increase cargo throughput. Also, policy makers should reconsider export-import duty policies that encourage trade friendliness to promote international maritime trade and effective/efficient cargo throughputs.</p>

1. Introduction

Nigeria is considered and has been rated amongst the poorest countries in the world. Although, this West African country has significant natural resources such as crude oil mineral resources, fish, forest, ocean and marine resources which can help the growth of the economy through international maritime trade. However, she is yet to be exceedingly productive, effective, and remarkable in the function of maritime trade and global shipping. It is clearly seen and a fact that approximately ninety percent (90%) of goods (cargo) coming in and going out of Nigeria is via the Nigerian ports, Apapa and Tincan Island ports. According to the United Nations conference on trade and development (UNCTAD, 2022) statistics, 291 ships were noted in the seaports of Nigeria in the year 2020. An obvious question is what are the effects of dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo and containerized cargo on cargo throughputs, vessel turnaround, and berth occupancy rate of ports in Nigeria? Usually, problem of obtaining statistics about the maritime trade items by type shipped through sea. Unfortunately, there is another critical problem in determining how the maritime trade elements are traded internationally by Nigerian affect the performance of ports in Nigeria. The difficulty of identifying the contribution of international maritime trade components towards the performance of ports in Nigeria especially, in the areas of cargo throughputs improvements.

While the government's priority is in agriculture and mining sector which will gear towards reviving the economy to sustainable heights, the maritime industry plays a significant role in fulfilling government's agenda through trading activities. Regardless of the enormous positive effects generated by maritime trade, negative and unfavourable effects have also engulfed the industry such as lack of maritime legal framework in Nigeria, reduced cargo throughputs, high vessel turnaround time, high intensity of berth occupancy rate, inadequate infrastructure, financial and environmental issues which are causing significant setback globally and affecting the performance of ports in Nigeria (Ndikom et al., 2017).

It is possible that maritime trade related factors negatively influencing the performance of Nigerian ports can be overcome or significantly reduced by the application of available port facilities and personnel. To achieve the proposed elimination or reduction at the level of negative influences imposed by the limiting factors empirical evidence and information are needed on which of the numerous factors constitute a significant factor and major clog in the wheel of operational progress efficiency and flow of maritime trade in Nigeria through the seaports. Expert inputs from oil and liquid bulk cargo/imports as major stakeholders and consumers of port services become very important in identifying the factors that inhibit the choice of ports for import and export hence there is the need to ascertain

how international maritime trade affects cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria.

In addition, the issues relevant to the analysis of demand for any maritime trade of the dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk and containerization suffer from a number of handling challenges which affect the free flow of international trade from the source to destination. This raises an all-embracing need to determine the effect of international maritime trade on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria. The demand for international maritime trade has necessitated the curiosity to measure its influence on the cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria.

1.1 Objectives of the Study

This study seeks to investigate the effect of international maritime trade on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria. Based on this the following objectives shall be achieved:

- 1) To determine the extent to which international maritime trade (dry bulk cargo) affect cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria.
- 1) To investigate the extent to which international maritime trade (liquid bulk cargo) affect cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria.
- 2) To find out the extent to which international maritime trade (containerized cargo) affect cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria.

1.2 Research Questions

This paper evaluates the effect of international maritime trade on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria. The following research questions have been raised and investigated in this study:

- 1) To what extent does dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo and containerized cargo affect cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria?
- 2) To what extent does international maritime trade (dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo and containerized cargo) affect cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria?
- 3) To what extent does international maritime trade (dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo and containerized cargo) affect cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria?

1.3 Conceptual Framework

This study seeks to evaluate the effect of international maritime trade on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria. In carrying out the study four dimensions of international maritime trade (independent variable or predictor variable) namely dry bulk cargo liquid bulk cargo containerized cargo and break bulks would be examined. These dimensions would be adopted in line with the works of Proshare (2020) and Olusegun (2020)

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Effect of International Maritime Trade on Vessel Turnaround Time of Ports in Nigeria

Sources: UNCTAD, (2023). Review of Maritime trade review of countries https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/rmt2023_ch7_en_1; Monday, E. I. Emenike, G.C. & Ibe C.C. (2021). Cargo throughput performance eastern ports. *World Journal of Innovative Research (WJIR)* 10 (6) 09-12;

1.4 Research Hypotheses

This research investigates the effect of international maritime trade on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria. Accordingly, the following hypotheses relating to the purpose and problems of the study have been formulated and for investigation:

- 1) *H01*: Dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo and containerized cargo have no significant effect cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria.
- 2) *H02*: Dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo and containerized cargo have no significant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria.
- 3) *H03*: Dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo and containerized cargo have no significant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

The literature review has captured concepts like- international maritime trade, dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo, containerized cargo and cargo

throughputs, empirical studies on the area of the study as well as the summary of the literature review with evidence of gaps in literature.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

In this section the theoretical framework underpinning the study has been explored. Theories such as: comparative advantage theory and theory of international trade have been x-rayed in this section.

2.1.1 Comparative Advantage Theory

This theory was propounded David Ricardo in 1817 because he was dissatisfied with the looseness in Smith's theory (Evans, 2011). According to Ricardo's theory of comparative advantage even if a nation has an absolute cost disadvantage in the production of both goods there still exists a basis for mutually beneficial trade. The less efficient nation should specialize in the production and exportation of the good in which it is relatively less inefficient (where its absolute disadvantage is least) while the more efficient nation should specialize in the production and exportation of the good in which it is relatively more efficient (where its absolute advantage is greatest). This theory proved to be better than Smith's absolute advantage theory because it is possible for a nation not to have an absolute advantage in anything, but it is not possible for one nation to have a comparative advantage in everything and the other nation to have a comparative advantage in nothing. That is because comparative advantage depends on relative costs (Rodrigue & Notteboom, 2020).

The comparative advantage theory in the principles of economics means the ability of a country to produce a particular commodity at a lower opportunity cost than another country. The concept further means the ability to produce a product most efficiently given all the other products that could be produced in the same market. Alderton (2008) opines that this theory can be contrasted with absolute advantage which means the ability of a country to produce a particular good at a lower absolute cost than another. The theory describes the manner in which trade can create value for both parties even when one can produce all commodities with fewer resources than the other (Jose & Tongzon, 2007). The net benefits of such an outcome are called gains from trade. Initial research on comparative advantage theory was first described by Robert Torrens in 1815 in an essay on the Corn Laws. He concluded it was England's advantage to trade with Poland in return for grain even though it might be possible to produce that grain more cheaply in England than Poland (Haberler, 1988).

2.1.2 Theory of International Trade

In the early 1900s a theory of international trade was developed by two Swedish economists Eli Heckscher and Bertil Ohlin. This theory has subsequently become known as the Heckscher-Ohlin model (H-O model) (Sanyal & Jones, 1982). The results of the H-O model are that the pattern of international trade is determined by differences in factor endowments. It predicts that countries will export those goods that make intensive use of locally abundant factors and will import goods that make intensive use of factors that are locally scarce (Sanyal & Jones, 1982).

The Heckscher-Ohlin model makes the following core assumptions (Ohlin, 1933): Labor and capital flow freely between sectors equalising factor prices across sectors within a country. The amount of labor and capital in two countries differ (difference in endowments). Technology is the same among countries (a long-term assumption), and tastes are the same upon countries.

International trade is in principle not different from domestic trade as the motivation and the behavior of parties involved in a trade does not change fundamentally depending on whether trade is across a border or not. The main difference is that international trade is typically more costly than domestic trade (Nelson et al., 2020). This study is adopting the theory of international trade because it provides a valuable insight into the nature of the link between international maritime trade and performance of ports. It is of a demand-driven link whereby oil and non-oil shipment growth stimulates maritime trade that add up to the growth berth occupancy rate and effective development of the ports. The theory of international trade allows for effective and efficient participation in crude oil and non-oil shipment, and it permits economies of scale not open to small - protected economies. By introducing greater market competition oil and non-oil shipment encourages a more efficient utilization of resources and greater growth/efficiency in cargo throughputs vessel turnaround time and berth occupancy rate of ports.

2.2 Conceptual Review

2.2.1 International Maritime Trade

International maritime trade is the one transacted by persons, companies, agencies or governments through the sea. [Stopford \(2009\)](#) defines maritime trade as the movement of merchandise by vessels between the ports of origin where merchandise is received from the exporter at the port of origin to the port of destination where merchandise is claimed by the importer. Maritime trade connects countries Markets Business and people allowing them to buy and sell goods all over the World. Seaborne Cargoes comprise commodities of different types and sizes. They can be grouped into six main categories: Energy trade Agriculture trade Metal industry trade Forest product Manufactured commodities ([Emi, 2016](#)). The history of the World is a history of exploration and trade by Sea.

[Iyoha and Okim \(2017\)](#) see seaborne oil trade as the exchange of petroleum resources (crude oil and refined oil resources) from and to supply and demand countries and its carriage and/or transportation by sea using ocean going tankers vessels. It is composed of seaborne dry bulk cargo and import trade and covers all kinds of petroleum energy resources whether crude oil or refined petroleum resources. Nigeria's seaborne oil trade comprises seaborne refined petroleum products import trade and crude dry bulk cargo trade via the Nigeria seaports and the dry bulk cargo terminals respectively; both categories of marine terminals being administered by the Nigeria Ports Authority (NPA).

[UNCTAD \(2021\) and Cariou \(2020\)](#) view seaborne as a mode of transport that has continued to represent the cheapest and most efficient means of moving very large volume of import and export trade goods in the Nigerian international trade. In Nigeria the seaborne sector has been responsible for facilitating over 90 percent of trading prospects. Nigeria accounts for over 60 percent of total seaborne traffic in volume and value in the West African subregion with a GDP accounting for over 60 percent of total GDP of 16 countries that make up the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS). The success or otherwise of the Nigeria seaborne trading sector therefore has a reverberating impact on the sub-region ([World Bank, 2020](#)). [Yusuf et al. \(2019\)](#) in their report on Global integration and the growth of Nigerians Liquid bulk cargo describe exporting as the process of earning profits by selling products or services in foreign markets. They indicate that the concept of exportation must be based on the principles of local sufficiency. This connotes that a country that will engage in any export trade mission should therefore as the case maybe, has such a product in large quantities and it must be easily available in reasonable sufficiency. As a resource-rich country Nigeria's economic performance has been unfortunately driven by only the oil and gas sector to the extent that even progress recorded towards genuine economic development prior to the discovering of oil in commercial quantity has been virtually eroded. In recent time between 2015 and 2017 the GDP growth was about 5.7 percent and the growth in the non-oil sector which contributed about 5.9 percent of the GDP ([Osidipe et al., 2018](#)).

2.2.2 Dry Bulk Cargo

A dry bulk commodity is a raw material that is shipped in large unpackaged parcels. Dry bulk consists of mostly unprocessed materials that are destined to be used in the global manufacturing and production process. The commodities, which can include grain, metal, and energy materials, are transported long distances in bulk by sea in large cargo vessels by companies that specialize in dry bulk delivery ([Adepoju, 2015](#)).

Dry bulk materials are unpackaged goods shipped in large parcels by sea and destined for manufacturers and producers. Coal, grains, and metals are examples of dry bulk commodities ([Booth, 2018](#)). The Baltic Dry Index (BDI) is a handy measure of prices paid for the transport of dry bulk materials. BDI is often viewed as a leading indicator of economic activity because changes in the index reflect the supply and demand for important materials used in manufacturing ([Agbo et al., 2018](#)). Dry bulk spillage is difficult to clean up as the items are usually in the millions and are either very small or the bulk item is a liquid.

Dry bulk goods are shipped in large amounts and are not package or transported the same way container transport is. Because of this, they are highly regulated to avoid spillage or contamination, and because dry bulk is more susceptible to factors such as temperature variance and other damages ([Eriksen, 2020](#)).

2.2.3 Liquid Bulk Cargo

Liquid bulk cargo is carried unpackaged in any quantity and usually transported by ships that are commonly referred to as tankers which are

built specially to make the loading and unloading process become easy ([Foyeku, 2019](#)). Liquid bulk cargo can be classified into various categories based on the nature of the liquid and its characteristics. Some common types of that include Crude Oil: Unrefined petroleum extracted from oil wells is transported to refineries for processing ([Eriksen, 2020](#)).

Liquid bulk cargo is of utmost importance in global trade, critical for industries such as energy, chemicals, and food and beverage. Its efficient transportation in bulk quantities ensures the availability of essential resources and fuels economic growth worldwide. Understanding the fundamentals of liquid bulk cargo is crucial for anyone involved in logistics, supply chain management, shipping, or related industries. ([Gicheru, 2020](#)). [Luke \(2020\)](#) posits that liquid bulk cargo can be classified into various categories based on the nature of the liquid and its characteristics. Some common types of that include Crude Oil: Unrefined petroleum extracted from oil wells is transported to refineries for processing. Petroleum Products: Refined products derived from crude oil, such as gasoline, diesel, jet fuel, and liquefied petroleum gas (LPG). Chemicals: A wide range of chemicals, including industrial chemicals, acids, solvents, fertilizers, and pharmaceutical ingredients. Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG): Natural gas cooled to a liquid state for efficient storage and transport. Food and Beverage Liquids: This includes edible oils, fruit juices, wine, milk, and other liquid food products. Each type of liquid bulk cargo requires specific handling, packaging, and transportation methods to ensure its integrity, safety, and compliance with regulations ([Park & Suh, 2019](#)).

Liquid bulk's loading process tends to be more complicated than other types of cargoes. First of all, it takes more times to clean the tanker if the liquids are leaked out from the vessels. After the ship arrives at the dock, the ship's officers and representatives of the terminal will check the cleanliness of the tankers. Once they approve, the loading process can be started ([Muhammad & Akanegbu, 2015](#)).

2.2.4 Containerized Cargo

Containerization, method of transporting freight by placing it in large containers. Containerization is an important cargo-moving technique developed in the 20th century ([Ally, 2015](#)). Road-and-rail containers, sealed boxes of standard sizes, were used early in the century; but it was not until the 1960s that containerization became a major element in ocean shipping, made possible by new ships specifically designed for container carrying. Large and fast, container ships carry containers above deck as well as below; and their cargoes are easily loaded and unloaded, making possible more frequent trips and minimum lost time in port.

The dimensions of containers have been standardized. The term twenty-foot-equivalent-unit (TEU) is used to refer to one container with a length of twenty feet. A container of 40 feet is expressed by 2 TEU ([Yakubu & Akanegbu, 2018](#)). Containerized cargo has revolutionized the shipping industry, making transporting goods worldwide more manageable and efficient. The concept of containerization involves using standardized containers to pack and ship various products, simplifying logistics processes and reducing costs ([Abdulrahman, 2021](#)).

Containerization has emerged as a vital component of international trade, transforming the way goods are transported, stored, and managed. With its standardized approach and efficient handling, containerization has significantly reduced transportation costs. It has improved supply chain efficiency and facilitated global commerce ([Zhang & Roe, 2018](#)).

Containerized trade distances have tumbled since 2020 but increased marginally in 2023. Intra-Asian containerized trade, which accounts for the majority of intraregional trade, saw its share increase over the years. As intra-Asian trade is carried over shorter distances, the average distances travelled per ton of container cargo of global containerized trade are relatively low. The predominance of intra-Asian containerized trade flows reflects global manufacturing patterns with China continuing to serve as the leader in global manufacturing, supported by neighbouring East Asian countries. It also reflects the growing participation of several East Asian countries in regional and global value chains ([UNCTAD, 2023](#)).

2.2.5 Cargo Throughputs

Cargo throughput means the volume of cargo handled at the Terminal in the period of one financial year. Port throughput measures reflect the amount of cargo or number of vessels the port handles over time. These measures are affected by many variables beyond physical capacity ([UNCTAD 2023](#)).

RESEARCH ARTICLE

It is worthy of note that average cargo throughput from 1956 to 2005 is 14467024 metric tons while the average cargo throughput from 2006 to 2012 is 67240231.86 metric tons. The yearly average cargo throughput of 67240231.86 metric tons of cargo from 2006 to 2012 over the yearly average of 14467024 metric tons from 1956 to 2005 shows a percentage increase of 456.69% (Lloyd & Odiegwu 2019). This shows the remarkable progress made in our port developmental efforts since the port concession era. In a nutshell the pattern in Nigerian port traffic during the pre-concession era is sinusoidal while the post concession experienced a sharp progressive rise. This means that between 2006 and 2017 cargo throughput at the nation's ports increased by over 67 per cent. This was as a result of the landlord model of port management which was adopted in 2006 that led to the concession of sections of the ports to private terminal operators otherwise called concessionaires and has led to the consistent improvement in cargo throughput (Odiegwu 2019). The situation reversed to the parallel trend from 1975-1987. This means that there was a downward tilt of the trend line. The period 1988-1999 witnessed a slight improvement in export activities with a slight upward tilt of the trend line while the trend line experienced a sharp upward movement from 2000-2022 (Odiegwu, 2019).

2.3 Empirical Review

Omoke et al., (2018) analyzed the impact of port operations on the Nigerian economy: A focus on Apapa seaport. Secondary data was sourced from the Nigeria Ports Authority's operational bulletin and analyzed with the multiple regression model using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 14.0. The study found that gross registered tonnage of vessels is significantly contributing to the Nigerian gross domestic product (GDP) at 0.05 significant level and that cargo throughput and vessel traffic have positive impact on the economy.

Adepoju (2020) investigated new seaport development-prospects and challenges: Perspectives from Apapa and Calabar Seaports. The purpose of the study was to examine and analyze the efficiencies of the Apapa and Calabar seaports in order to determine the need for any investment in seaport development. Descriptive analysis and stochastic frontier analysis (SFA) were used to examine seaports' challenges and determine the efficiency of the ports. Secondary data and responses of the stakeholders and shipping companies were collected through 2008–2017 cargo throughputs of the selected seaports and a well-structured questionnaire. The study found draught level cost of shipment ease of access to industries and condition of other modes of transportation as major challenges linked to the Calabar Seaport but found the Lagos Apapa seaport quite efficient. The study recommended that investment decisions to build a new seaport or dredge to upgrade the existing ones should be analyze carefully as demand should be the driving force for new port establishment: when a port cannot generate enough traffic it may not yield returns on investment as expected.

Emenike et al., (2018) on the assessment of vessel traffic and customers' patronage at the Rivers seaport Port Harcourt Nigeria explained about the contribution of cargo handling equipment to port performance. The study suggests that approximately 80 percent of world merchandise trade carried by ships maritime transport remains by far the most common mode of international freight transport.

Ndikom et al. (2018) investigated the influence of time on seaborne oil trade in Nigeria. The study used the statistical tools of trend analysis simple regression analysis and independent sample t-test to analyze the data obtained. The study found that there is a significant difference between the export oil trade and import oil trade. The difference favours sea borne dry bulk cargo trade indicating that more dry bulk cargo trade has been handled/facilitated by the seaports over the time period covered in the study than containerized cargo trade.

Bensassi et al., (2019) empirically examine the effect of FDI inflows into Nigeria on real gross domestic product (RGDP) growth and how these external inflows can bring about achieving goal-of mobilizing additional financial resources for developing countries from multiple sources. The study found that labour quality has a positive and significant effect on RGDP in line with theory. Omodero and Alpheaus (2019) carried out a study on the effect of foreign debt on the economic growth of Nigeria. The regression results indicate that foreign debt exerts a significant negative influence on economic growth while foreign debt servicing has a strong and significant positive impact on economic growth. Oladimeji and Muhammed (2017) investigated the effect of international business on SMEs growth in a competitive environment particularly Nigeria. It was also

revealed that the exchange rate has a significant effect on SMEs growth in Nigeria and the level at which exchange rate affects SMEs growth is relatively high. Osabohien et al., (2019) investigated the impact of agricultural export on Nigeria's economic growth. The results from the ARDL technique revealed that agricultural exports significantly affect Nigeria's economic growth this suggests that a 1percent increase in agricultural export will boost economic growth in Nigeria by approximately 25 percent.

2.3.1 Effect of International maritime trade on Cargo Throughputs

Adepoju (2020) examined new seaport development-prospects and challenges: Perspectives from Apapa and Calabar Seaports and found that imports and exports are accounted for in a country's current account in the foreign exchange. International Trading may give consumers and countries the opportunity to be exposed to new markets and products. Almost every kind of product can be found in the international market ranging from food clothes spare parts oil dry bulks wine stocks currencies and water. Services such as tourism banking consulting and transportation.

Onyema et al. (2015) conducted a study on comparative analysis of port performance in Nigeria: A study of ports in Rivers State. The study used descriptive statistical tools to analyse the data. The study revealed that international trade is very crucial to the continuance of globalization. Countries are limited to the goods and services produced within their own borders without international maritime trade. The benefits of international maritime trade have been the major drivers of growth for the last half of the 20th century.

Also Saeed et al., (2021) did a study exploring the relationships between maritime connectivity international trade and domestic production. With the help of regression analysis, the study found that nations with strong international maritime trade have become prosperous and have the power to control the world economy. The study further revealed that international maritime trade can become one of the major contributors to the reduction of poverty. The study asserts that no country in the world can sustain itself or survive without exchanging goods and services with other countries in the world.

Monday et al., (2021) examined cargo throughput performance in eastern ports. The study used correlational analytical tools and found that cargo throughputs of Nigeria depend on her trade with other nations to a large extent. The study further revealed that Nigeria as a developing country has been struggling with realities of developmental process not only politically and socially but also economically too. Ndikom et al., (2017) did an assessment of the relationship among cargo-throughput vessel turnaround time and port revenue in Nigeria: A study of Lagos port complex. Using multiple regression analysis, they found that maritime trade has made an increasingly significant impact on cargo throughputs. They further revealed that the openness of a nation determines a country's growth rate by impacting upon the level of economic activities and facilitating the transfer of resources across borders. Nigeria is an open economy with international transactions significantly contributing to her output.

Munim and Schramm (2018) examined the impacts of port infrastructure and logistics performance on economic growth: The mediating role of maritime trade. The study used multiple regression analysis and chi-Square statistical tools with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences software (SPSS) the study found that international maritime trade has strong indications of fostering peace and mutual understanding among nations as port cargo throughputs grow tremendously. The study therefore hypothesizes that: Ho1: Dry bulk cargo has no significant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria. Ho2: Liquid bulk cargo has no significant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria. Ho3: Containerized cargo has no significant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria.

Figure 2: Operationalized Framework of the Effect of International Maritime Trade on Cargo Throughputs of Ports in Nigeria
Sources: UNCTAD, (2023). Review of Maritime trade review of countries https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/rmt2023_ch7_en.1;
Monday, E. I. Emenike, G.C. & Ibe C.C. (2021). Cargo throughput performance eastern ports. *World Journal of Innovative Research (WJIR)* 10 (6) 09-12;

2.4 Summary of Literature Review and Gap

The literature review carried out so far has revealed that the subject of this research is partially lacking in existing literature as some of the relevant concepts are seemingly fresh and related to international maritime trade and performance of ports in Nigeria in particular. However, the context of dry bulk cargo and liquid bulk cargo in Nigeria show that the country would have fared better if not for lack of proper dry bulk and liquid bulk cargo which has greatly hampered any efforts at monitoring the trend of activities in Nigerian seaports. The current state of Nigeria's dry bulk and liquid bulk cargo in the international market were also found to be unfavourable. The review of literature shows gaps in literature in certain areas and issues that are very germane in international maritime trade. It is revealed from the literature that international maritime trade and performance of ports in Nigeria have not been studied in Nigeria extensively. Generally, the poor quality of service occasioned by time wasting behaviour of ports is still a critical outstanding problem that Nigerian ports urgently need to solve in order to achieve effective maritime trade performance objectives. In view of this the work will attempt to explore the effect of international maritime trade and performance of ports in Nigeria.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted the ex-post facto research design which requires the usage of historical data to forecast future trends employing regression techniques. The focus of an ex-post facto research design is to effectively explain the characteristics of a population or a social phenomenon in the past (Akujuru & Enyioko, 2018 and Saeed et al. 2021).

3.2 Method of Data Collection

Secondary sources of data were used. The relevant data for this study were collected from the annual reports and accounts of Nigerian Ports Authority, National Bureau of Statistics and Central Bank of Nigeria Annual Statistical Bulletins of the various years in question from their official website. The data collected were from the period of 1991-2023.

3.3 Apriori Expectation

The apriori expectations adopted the findings of Odiegwu and Enyioko (2022a); Chang et al. (2020); Agbo et al. (2018) which all stated a positive significant effect of international maritime trade on vessel turnaround time. Under this model testing, the descriptive and stationarity testing were done on all the variables and apriori reasoning that the port performance indicators will flow in the same direction as international maritime trade (Lloyd & Odiegwu, 2019; Nwaogbe et al. 2020).

3.4 Model Specification

This research work adopts the model of Odiegwu and Enyioko (2022a) and Chang et al. (2020) with slight modifications. The researchers expressed vessel turnaround time as a function of International Maritime Trade (IMT). Their models are stated thus:

$$CTP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DBC + \beta_2 LBC + \beta_3 CC + Ut \text{ -----} 1$$

$$CTP = f(DBC, LBC, CC) \text{ -----} 2$$

Where; CTP = Cargo Throughputs; DBC = Dry Bulk Cargo; LBC = Liquid Bulk Cargo

CC= Containerized Cargo

3.5 Pre-Estimation Test:

The following pre-estimation tests were carried out in this study:

3.5.1 Unit not Test

Following Dickey and Fuller (1979, 1981), Levin, Lin and. Chu (2002) considered a panel extension of the null hypothesis that each individual time series in the panel contains a unit root against the alternative hypothesis that all individual series are stationary. The ADF test involves estimating the model, obtaining the test statistic, and comparing it with critical values in order to decide on the rejection of the null hypothesis or otherwise.

3.5.2 Cointegration Test

Unit root variables (or non-stationary time series) do not meet this assumption, hence, any hypothesis tested will produce skewed, biased or misleading results.

3.6 Data Analysis Techniques

The Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) model was used as analytical technique. Researchers employ the ARDL estimator owing to its numerous benefits, including the fact that all the data series under consideration do not need to have the same order of integrations, regardless of whether the regressors have an I (0) or I (1) order of cointegration. All these analyses were computed through the use of E-view statistical package version 10. **Post Estimation Test:** The study conducted the following post estimation tests: Normality Test: Normality tests are statistical procedures used in ascertaining whether the errors or residuals in a regression model follow a normal distribution or not.

4. Results

This section focused on the data presentation, data analysis and discussion of results on the Effect of International Maritime Trade on Cargo Throughputs of Ports in Nigeria (1990-2023).

4.1 Data Presentation

Table 1 Presentation of the Raw Data for the Study

Effect of International Maritime Trade on Cargo Throughputs of Ports in Nigeria (1990-2023)

Date	International Maritime Trade			Cargo Throughputs of Ports in Nigeria
Date	Dry Bulk Cargo (M/T (000000))	Liquid Bulk Cargo (M/T (000000))	Containerized Cargo (Per unit) TEU	Cargo Throughputs M/T (000000)
1990	4022218	5327912	123101	45.6
1991	8553527	5554690	136230	42.9
1992	9397988	5781825	152791	40.8
1993	9377242	7397837	135342	43.9
1994	7368492	8128978	111300	46.5
1995	5022272	6977933	196888	51.1
1996	4543878	1951427	199844	53.4
1997	3002846	3420943	236683	55.6
1998	4316408	4446979	286657	58.3
1999	4479593	5032791	344354	60.2
2000	6022251	6327912	344229	57.3
2001	9553569	5554690	483223	60.5
2002	9397988	5781825	545797	63.4
2003	10377285	7397837	588593	66.9
2004	10368487	8128978	513954	71.5
2005	12335850	7152143	575242	65.6
2006	11334417	19279472	637055	70.3
2007	12082132	18722189	431950	74.9
2008	11212278	20734912	612982	78.5
2009	19116321	19395412	653584	75.1
2010	12968477	21227241	685937	74.1
2011	13082771	25234551	839977	76.8
2012	10102158	24914764	880597	80.4
2013	9693134	22405332	992666	84.1
2014	9651053	24412213	1063486	87.2
2015	9170517	23343142	939379	87.5
2016	9704453	21813543	808587	75.1
2017	9818494	24287916	822706	81.9
2018	8729495	24066957	775842	101.7
2019	8887067	25404145	344354	97.9
2020	9971872	23972824	344229	79.4
2021	9895774	25837493	483180	103.9
2022	9798865	26217957	545797	108.6
2023	9984417	26571541	588596	54.8

Sources: Nigerian Ports Authority (NPA) National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) Nigerian Shippers Council (NSC). Central Bank of Nigeria 1990-2023

4.2 Pre-Estimation Test Trend Analysis

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Figure 1: Time Plot on Dry Bulk Cargo
Source: Researcher's (2025) Extract from Eviews 12.0 output

Figure.1 shows graphical presentation of dry bulk cargo's contribution as a predictor variable to international maritime trade from 1990 to 2023. The value of dry bulk cargo's contribution to international maritime trade gradually increased from 4 billion to 8 billion between 1990 and 1993 and started fluctuating/declining drastically from 1994 to 1997. Similarly, dry bulk cargo's contribution to international maritime increased to 20 billion in 2010 and thereafter started declining till 2020 when it started stabilizing.

Figure 2: Time Plot on Liquid Bulk Cargo
Source: Researcher's (2025) Extract from Eviews 12.0 output

Figure 2 shows graphical presentation of liquid bulk cargo's contribution as a predictor variable to international maritime trade from 1990 to 2023. The value of liquid bulk cargo's contribution to international maritime trade fluctuated all through from 1990 to 2020 with increasing tempo. The highest increase was recorded between 2010 to 2013 to 25 billion.

Figure 3: Time Plot on Containerized Cargo
Source: Researcher's (2025) Extract from Eviews 12.0 output

Figure 3 shows graphical presentation of containerization's contribution as a predictor variable to international maritime trade from 1990 to 2023. The value of liquid containerization's contribution to international maritime trade rose steadily from 1990 to 2020 with the highest increase in 2015 to the tone of 1 billion.

Figure 4: Time Plot on Cargo Throughputs
Source: Researcher's (2025) Extract from Eviews 12.0 output

Figure 4.4 shows the trend presentation of cargo throughput's contribution as a measure to performance of ports in Nigeria from 1990 to 2023. The value of cargo throughput's input in the performance of ports in Nigeria increased steadily from 45 to 70 (M/T 000000) between 1990 and 2004 and declined drastically to 25 (M/T 000000) in 2005. Equally, cargo throughput's contribution to performance of ports in Nigeria started increasing in the later part of 2005 from 30 (M/T 000000) to 105 (M/T 000000) in 2021.

4.3 Data Analysis

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for international maritime trade and performance of ports in Nigeria

	DBC	CC	LBC	CTP
Mean	9215989.	512503.9	15064891	68.82647
Median	9672094.	529875.5	19000831	70.90000
Maximum	19116321	1063486.	26571541	108.6000
Minimum	3002846.	111300.0	1951427.	30.00000
Std. Dev.	3142834.	273989.7	9025356.	19.34772
Skewness	0.336204	0.203042	-0.056107	0.145207
Kurtosis	4.618403	2.043747	1.201256	2.406016
Jarque-Bera	4.351093	1.529041	4.601435	0.619305
Probability	0.113546	0.465557	0.100187	0.733702
Sum	3.13E+08	17425132	5.12E+08	2340.100
Sum Sq. Dev.	3.26E+14	2.48E+12	2.69E+15	12353.03
Observations	34	34	34	34

Source: Researcher's (2025) Extract from Eviews 12.0 output

Note: DBC -Dry Bulk Cargo, CC -Containerized Cargo, LBC -Liquid Bulk Cargo, CT-Cargo Throughputs

Table 2 shows the results of descriptive statistics for dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo, containerized cargo, cargo throughputs, vessel turnaround time, berth occupancy rate and export duty. The results of descriptive statistics show that all the variables, dry bulk cargo, containerized cargo, liquid bulk cargo have positive average values. This simply means they are positively mean reverting. the variables Dry Bulk Cargo, Containerized Cargo and Cargo Throughputs are positively skewed to the right whereas Liquid Bulk Cargo is negatively skewed to the right. The study also tested for data normality using Jarque-Bera normality test. Also, all the variables were found to be normally distributed since the P-values for Jarque-Bera test were greater than 0.05 for the variables.

Table 3: Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) and Phillip Perron (PPT) Unit Root Test for international maritime trade and Cargo Throughputs of ports in Nigeria

Variables	Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF)		Phillip Perron Test (PPT)	
	Level (1(0))	First Diff (1(1))	Level (1(0))	First Diff (1(1))
DBC	-2.560(0.111)	-7.736(0.000)	-2.506(0.232)	-7.638(0.000)
CC	-1.617(0.62)	-5.163(0.00)	-1.633(0.55)	-5.147(0.00)
LBC	-0.693(0.835)	-6.670(0.000)	-0.575(0.63)	-6.675(0.000)
CTP	-1.360(0.89)	-7.149(0.00)	-2.391(0.52)	-7.920(0.000)

Source: Researcher's (2025) Extract from Eviews 12.0 output

Note: DBC -Dry Bulk Cargo, CC - Containerized Cargo, LBC -Liquid Bulk Cargo, CTP-Cargo Throughputs

Table 3 contains the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test results on export duty international maritime trade and performance of ports in Nigeria. The results for both Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) and showed that the estimated probability values of all the variables under investigations are greater than significant at the 5% level of significance.

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Therefore, we can reject the null hypothesis. This simply means the series are stationary at level. However, the Phillip Peron (PP) Unit root test was applied to further differentiated the series to ensure stationarity. The results obtained for Phillip Peron (PP) unit root test showed that the estimated probability values of all the variables under investigations were less than the standard probability value (0.005) at the 5% level of significance at first difference. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis. This simply means there is no presence of unite root (stationary) at first difference.

4.4 Co-Integration Tests

The Johansen co-integration test was done to determine whether there is a long run relationship between the variables under investigations using the trace and max-eigen test statistics. The results of the Johansen co-integration test are shown in Table 4:

Hypothesize d	Trace 0.05			Max-Eigen 0.05				
	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Prob.*	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Prob.*		
None	0.46352	35.434	47.85	0.425	0.463521	19.927	27.58	0.346
At most 1	0.27024	15.507	29.79	0.746	0.270244	10.081	21.131	0.7370
At most 2	0.136110	5.4261	15.49	0.762	0.136110	4.6819	14.26	0.7813
At most 3	0.022989	0.744	3.841	0.388	0.02298	0.7442	3.841	0.388

Table 4: Results of the Johansen Co-integration Test Dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo, containerized cargo and cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria
Source: Researcher's Extract from Eviews 12.0 output

Table 4 contains the results of the Johansen co-integration test for Dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo and containerized cargo and cargo throughputs. The results of the coefficient of none * and at most 2 * showed that the estimated probability value of (0.4253, 0.7463, 0.7620 and 0.3883) and (0.3462, 0.7370, 0.7813 and 0.3883) for both the trace and maximum eigenvalue for the variables under investigations are significant at the 5% level of significance. The null hypothesis of no co-integration is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there one long run equilibrium (relationship) between the variables. There is no co-integration equation between Dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo and containerized cargo and cargo throughputs

Table 5: Results of the Johansen Co-Integration Test for international maritime trade

Hypothesize d	Trace 0.05			Max-Eigen 0.05				
	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Prob.*	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Prob.*		
None	0.4646	34.09	29.79	0.1151	0.464611	19.992	21.131	0.0716
At most 1	0.3466	14.100	15.49	0.080	0.346671	13.621	14.26	0.063
At most 2	0.0148	0.479	3.841	0.488	0.014866	0.4792	3.841	0.488
At most 3	0.4646	34.09	29.79	0.1151	0.464611	19.992	21.131	0.0716

Table 5 contains the results of the Johansen co-integration test for international maritime trade and cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria. The results of the coefficient of none * and at most 3 * showed that the estimated probability value of (0.1151, 0.0802, 0.4887 and 0.1151) and (0.0716, 0.0630, 0.4887 and 0.0716) for both the trace and maximum eigenvalue for the variables under investigations are significant at the 5% level of significance. The null hypothesis of no co-integration is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there one long run equilibrium (relationship) between international maritime trade and performance of ports in Nigeria. There no co-integration equation that exists between international maritime trade and cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria.

4.5 Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1, 2 and 3

H01: Dry bulk cargo has no significant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria. H02: Liquid bulk cargo has no significant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria. H03: Containerized cargo has no significant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria.

Table 6: Results of The Hypothesis Testing on the Effect of Dry Bulk Cargo, Ports In Nigeria

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t-Statistic	Significant/Probability Value	Decision
	B	Std. Error	Beta	Std. Error			
1 (Constant)	46.784	6.195			7.552	.000	
DBC	-6.968	0.000	-.116	0.000	-0.878	.388	Insignificant
CC	1.404	.000	.211	0.000	1.355	.186	Insignificant
LBC	1.473	.000	.722	0.000	4.424	.000	Significant

Dependent Variable: CTP i.e. Cargo Throughput

b: Predictors: Dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo, containerized cargo

Source: Researcher's (2025) Extract from Eviews 12.0 output

$$Y_1 = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_3x_3 + e \quad (1) \text{ \{Model\}}$$

$$Y_1(\text{Cargo Throughput}) = 46.784 - 6.968\text{DBC} + 1.404\text{CC} + 1.473\text{LBC} + e$$

$$t = \quad \quad \quad (-0.878) \quad (1.355) \quad (4.424)$$

Table 6 shows the results of the test of hypothesized statements – H01 of model 1. The result of the hypotheses 1, 2 and 3 tested, show negative and insignificant effect of dry bulk cargo on cargo throughputs with t- value outcome of -0.878 @ p0.388 > 0.05, meaning that dry bulk cargo has negative effect which is not significant on cargo throughputs. The result further revealed that positive and insignificant effect of containerized cargo on cargo throughputs with t- value outcome of t = 1.355 @ p0.186 > 0.05 -meaning that containerized cargo has insignificant effect on cargo throughputs of ports. Also, the analysis in Table 6 revealed positive and significant effect of liquid bulk cargo on cargo throughputs with t-value outcome of 4.424 @ p0.000 < 0.05, therefore, liquid bulk cargo has significant effect on cargo throughputs of ports". Conclusively, the study has revealed that dry bulk cargo has negative/significant effect on cargo throughputs, liquid bulk cargo has positive/significant effect on cargo throughputs and containerized cargo has no significant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria.

The results for cusum test for model diagnostic check are shown in Figure 5

Figure 5: Result for cusum model diagnostic check for the effect of dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo, containerized cargo on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria

Source: Researcher's (2025) Extract from Eviews 12.0 output

The result for cusum model diagnostic check for the effect of dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo, containerized cargo on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria is shown in Figure 5. The results of cusum shows that the lines lie within the 95 percent confident bound. This shows that cusum for the model diagnostic check for the effect of dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo, containerized cargo on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria is adequate for forecasting and policy formulation.

Figure 6: Result for normality test for model diagnostic check for the effect of dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo, containerized cargo on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria

Source: Researcher's (2025) Extract from Eviews 12.0 output

Figures 5 and 6 show result for cusum and normality diagnostic check for the effect of dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo, containerized cargo on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria. Also, estimated value of the Jarque-Bera and its associated estimated probability value 0.071536 is greater than the standard probability value of 0.05. This shows that the hypothesis test shown normality test for the model is accepted. Therefore, the model for effect of dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo, containerized cargo on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria is adequate for forecasting and policy formulation

Table 7: Summary of the Results on Test of the Research Hypotheses

Research Hypotheses	t-value	Significant/Probability Value	Result	Decision
H01: Dry bulk trade has no significant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria	0.102	0.919	Positive and Insignificant	Accept
H02: Liquid bulk trade has no significant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria	-0.836	0.410	Negative and Insignificant effect	Accept
H03: Containerized trade has no significant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria	2.176	0.038	Positive and Significant effect	Reject

Source: Research Data 2025, and IBM SPSS Statistics 26 Window Output

5. Discussion

Effect of International Maritime Trade (Dry Bulk Cargo; Liquid Bulk Cargo and Containerized Cargo) on Cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria

The study found positive, negative and insignificant effect of international maritime trade on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria, and this points to the fact that, dry bulk cargo is one of the biggest channels through which international maritime trade in Nigeria could achieve efficiency in vessel turnaround time. A diagnostic examination of the findings with refence to all the four variables reveals that dry bulk cargo has no significant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria (t = 0.102); liquid bulk cargo has negative and insignificant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria (t = -0.836); containerized cargo has positive and significant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria).

To support this assertion Balogun (2016) contends that liquid bulk cargo as a dimension for maritime trade is one of the best platforms to mobilize trade through ports. Badejo and Solaja (2017) also found that a strong and significant relationship exist between liquid bulk cargo and berth occupancy rate of ports in Nigeria.

The study found that liquid bulk cargo offers veritable opportunities to optimize international maritime trade efficiency in ports by helping to convert resources, build traffic intensity in trade and engage customers and stakeholders to utilize ports for their international business transactions. The reality of this finding is that dry bulk cargo and liquid bulk cargo have become potent vehicles in maritime trade as controlled by ports to promote exports and imports of dry bulk cargo and liquid bulk cargo orientations. These findings agree with the views of Azam and Feng (2022) that dry bulk cargo and liquid bulk cargos are important aspects of international maritime trade consummated through port operations. They maintain that liquid bulk cargo delivers on shipping activities of

international dimension, it supports the of increase sales, engenders leads and advances trade and commerce. The OLS results for the effect of dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo, containerized cargo on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria. The OLS regression analysis reveals that liquid bulk cargo has a positive and significant impact on vessel turnaround time in Nigerian ports, while dry bulk cargo and containerized cargo are not significant. However, the low R-squared value of 0.177967 indicates that only 17.79% of the variation in vessel turnaround time is explained by the independent variables, suggesting that other factors contribute to vessel turnaround time. The Johansen co-integration test shows a long-run equilibrium relationship between dry bulk cargo, liquid bulk cargo, containerized cargo, and vessel turnaround time, indicating that these variables are co-integrated. The Granger causality test reveals a unidirectional causality from dry bulk cargo to liquid bulk cargo, but no bidirectional causality between the variables. Model diagnostic checks using cusum and normality tests show mixed results. The cusum test indicates that the model is adequate for forecasting and policy fomulation, but the normality test reveals non-normality, questioning the model's adequacy. These findings are consistent with existing literature on port efficiency and vessel turnaround time. For instance, a study by Tongzon (2009) found that cargo type and volume significantly impact vessel turnaround time. Similarly, a study by Cullinane et al. (2012) revealed that port efficiency and infrastructure are crucial factors in reducing vessel turnaround time. Other studies have explored the relationship between cargo mix and vessel turnaround time. For example, a study by Haralambides (2002) found that dry bulk cargo has a significant impact on vessel turnaround time. However, the results contradict some studies that found significant relationships between containerized cargo and vessel turnaround time (Barros, 2006; Banker & Chang, 2006). The study also revealed that the quality of interaction between maritime trade and vessel turnaround time in ports relates to key performance decisions in ports. On this Booth (2018) submits that maritime trade is best deployed as integral part of global business with broader trading strategy that elicits the attraction of internal customers/client and stakeholders to the ports.

6. Conclusion

International maritime trade is a pivotal avenue for the movement of merchandise by vessels between the port of origin where merchandise is received from the exporter at the port of origin to the port of destination where merchandise is claimed by the importer. It has the ability to impact on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria and other businesses when conducted effectively and efficiently within the categorization of best international trade practices. Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions have been made:

Dry bulk trade has positive and insignificant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria (t-value = 0.102@ p0.919>0.05). Liquid bulk trade has negative and insignificant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria (t-value = -0.836@ p0.410>0.05). Containerized trade has positive and significant effect on cargo throughputs of ports in Nigeria (t-value = 2.176@ p0.038>0.05).

7. Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- 1) Nigerian ports should prioritize and utilize the full capacity available in maritime trade and articulate on dry and liquid bulk cargo handling to improve the increase cargo throughput and reduce berth occupancy rates.
- 2) Nigerian ports should encourage the export of dry bulk cargoes and liquid bulk cargoes by putting up facilities, infrastructures and conducive environment necessary for investment in port that encourage the optimization of cargo throughputs of ports.
- 3) Policy makers should reconsider export-import duty policies that encourage trade friendliness to promote international maritime trade and effective and efficient operations in handling cargo throughputs.

Funding sources:

This study did not receive any grant from funding agencies.

Declaration of authors' conflict of interest:

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

References

- AdedayoAbdulrahman, B.M.A. (2021). Oil and liquid bulk trade on economic performance in Saudi Arabia. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 11(1), 88-92.
- Adepoju, O. O. (2020). New seaport development-prospects and challenges: Perspectives from Apapa and Calabar Seaports Nigeria. *Logistics* 4 (8) 1-12.
- Adepoju, O.O. (2015). *Analysis of Logistics Network Systems in Shipping Operations of Selected Nigerian Seaports*. Master's Thesis *Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Ogbomoso Nigeria*.
- Agbo, E.I., Agu. E. & Eze. L.O. (2018). Impact of international trade on the economic growth of Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management* 10 18.
- Ajayi, E.O. & Araoye, F.E. (2019). Trade openness and economic Growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and financial Management*.4 (2) 25-45.
- Akujuru, C. A. & Enyioko, N. C. (2018). Social science research: Methodology and conceptual perspectives. *Beau Bassin: Lambert Academic Publishing*.
- Ally, R. S. (2015). *The Role of Seaport in Facilitating Growth of Trade in Tanzania: A Case study of Dar Es Salaam Port A Dissertation Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of Masters in Business Administration in Transport and Logistics Management*. Tanzania
- Azam, M. & Feng, Y. (2022). Does foreign aid stimulate economic growth in Developing countries? Further evidence in both aggregate and disaggregated samples. *Quality and Quantity* 56(2)533-556.
- Badejo, B.A. & Solaja, O.M. (2017). The Nigerian seaports and development (1900- 2015): Historical perspectives and dynamics. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability* 6 (9) 1007-1024.
- Bensassi, S. Jarreau, J. & Mitaritonna. C. (2019). Regional Integration and Informal Trade in Africa: Evidence from Benin's Borders. *Journal of African Economies* 28: 89-118.
- Booth, L. (2018). Ports Critical for Growth in Africa. www.commercialriskonline.com/ports-critical-growth-africa/.
- Cariou, P. (2020). Changing demand for maritime trade International Transport Forum Discussion Paper of Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) *International Transport Forum Paris*.
- Comtois, C. & Slack, B. (2018). *Ship turnaround times in port: comparative analysis of ocean container carriers*. *Canada Interuniversity Research Centre on Enterprise Networks Logistics and Transportation*.
- Emenike, G.C., Amamilo, A.C. & Ajayi, A.O. (2018). Assessment of Vessel Traffic and Customers Patronage at the Rivers Seaport Port Harcourt Rivers State Nigeria. *Nature and Science*; 16 (11) 22-29.
- Emi, M. O. (2016). *Re-inventing Port Harcourt as a Shipping Hub*. <https://businessday.ng/analysis/article/re-inventing-port-harcourt>.
- Eniola, O. J., Njoku, I. Oluwatosin, F.A. & Okoko, E. (2014). Performance evaluation of Nigerian Ports: Pre and post concession eras. *Journal of Civil and Environmental Research* 6 (2), 70- 85.
- Eriksen, I.E (2020). *The Demand for Bulk Ship Services*. New York: Menbra Hill Inc; 8th edition.
- Esmer, S. (2008). *Performance Measurements of Container Terminal Operations*: <http://www.sbe.deu.edu.tr/dergi/cilt10.say%C4%B110.1%20esmer>
- Evans, W. R. (2011). Is Openness Inflationary? Policy Commitment and Imperfect Competition. *Journal of Macroeconomics* 34: 1095-110.
- Farahane M. & Heshmati A. (2020). Trade and Economic Growth: Theories and Evidence from the Southern African Development Community.
- Foyeku, S. (2019). *Ship Owners Accuse Customs of Sabotaging Cabotage Law Implementation*. <https://shipsandports.com.ng/ship-owners-accuse-customs-of-sabotaging-cabotage-law>
- Gicheru, B. (2020). *Modernization Milestones at Mombasa Port East Africa's Regional Hub*. <https://www.maritime-executive.com/editorials/modernization-milestones-at-mombasa-port-east-africa-s-regional-hub>.
- Haberler, G. (1988). *International Trade and Economic Development*. San Francisco CA: *International Center for Economic Growth*.
- Ibe, C.C. & Onwuegbuchunam, D.E. (2012). Cargo dwell time and efficiency of Nigeria's seaports: A production frontier analysis. *International Business Management Journal* 5(6)382-387.
- Jose, L. & Tongzon, B. (2007). *Port Choice and Freight Forwarders*. *Graduate School of Logistics Inha University 253 Yonghyun-Dong Nam-ku Incheon 402-751 South Korea*.
- Kang, D. & Kim, S. (2017). Conceptual model development of sustainability practices: The case of port operations for collaboration and governance. *Sustainability* 9 2333.
- Kim, S. & Chiang, B.G. (2017). The role of sustainability practices in international port operations: An analysis of moderation effect. *Journal Korea Trade* 21.
- Lee, P.T.W., Lam, J.S.L., Lin, C.W. & Hu, K.C. & Cheong, I. (2018). Developing the Fifth Generation Port Concept Model: An Empirical Test *International Journal of Logistics Management* 29(3) 1098-1120.
- Lloyd, C. J. & Odiegwu, C. L. (2019). Effect of liner shipping on container terminal performance of Apapa and Onne ports in Nigeria. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)* 8(10) 1336-1353
- Luke, D. (2020). *Why Trade Matters for African Development*. <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/businessreview/2020/08/25/why-trade-matters-for-african-development>.
- Monday, E. I. Emenike, G.C. & Ibe C.C. (2021). Cargo throughput performance in eastern ports. *World Journal of Innovative Research (WJIR)* 10 (6) 09-12.
- Moon, D. (2018). *Terminal performance measures*. Malmö Sweden World Maritime University.
- Muhammad, M.Y. & Akanegbu, B.N. (2015). The impact of international trade on economic growth in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business Economics and Accountancy*. 3. 6.
- Munim, Z. H. & Schramm H. J. (2018). The impacts of port infrastructure and logistics performance on economic growth: the mediating role of maritime trade. *Journal of Shipping and Trade* 3(1), 1.
- Ndikom, O.B., Buhari, S.O. & Nwokedi, T.C. (2017). An assessment of the relationship among cargo throughput vessel turnaround time and port revenue in Nigeria: A study of Lagos port complex. *Journal of Advance Research in Business Management and Accounting* 3(7) 1-13.
- Nelson, O. N., Gladice, O.S., Rivel, B.P.D. & Yirong, Y. (2020). Impact of exports on economic growth in the non-oil sector in the republic of Congo. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 12(3), 1-10.
- Nigerian Ports Authority, (2018). *Annual Statistical Bulletin Marina Lagos Nigeria Ports Authority (NPA) (2023)*. Annual Abstract of Ports Statistics, Nwamuo C. (2019). Impact of International Trade on Economic Growth: The Nigerian Experience. *European Journal of Business and Management* 11 34.
- Nwaogbe, O.R., Pius, A., Abduljeli, A. & Alharahsheh, H.H. (2020). An empirical study of Nigerian seaports operational performance. *Transport & Logistics: The International Journal* 20(48)73-87.
- Odiegwu, C. L. (2019). Effect of tramp shipping on container terminal performance of Apapa and Onne Ports in Nigeria. *Rivers State University Journal of Strategic and Internet Business* 4 (2) 556-588. www.rsuisb.com.
- Odiegwu, C. L. & Enyioko, N. C. (2022a). Effect of abandoned vessels on safety of mariners in coastal waters of Nigeria. *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science* 4 (8) 2352 - 2370 www.irjmets.com.
- Odiegwu, C. L. & Enyioko, N. C. (2022b). Influence of sustainable shipping on organizational effectiveness of shipping companies in Port Harcourt Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)* VI VIII 74 -92.
- Ohlin, B. (1933). *Interregional and international trade*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Okwedy, N. (2020). *The problem with ports in Nigeria*. <https://www.stearsng.com/article/the-problem-with-nigerias-ports>.
- Olaogbebikan, J.E., Njoku, I. Faniran, A.O. & Okoko, E. (2014). Performance evaluation of Nigerian ports: Pre and post concession eras. *Civil and Environmental Research* 6(2), 475-514.

RESEARCH ARTICLE

- Olusegun, O. A. (2020). New seaport development-prospects and challenges: perspectives from Apapa and Calabar seaports Nigeria. *Logistics* 4(2), 1-12.
- Omodero, C.O. & Alpheaus O.E. (2019). The effect of foreign debt on the Economic Growth of Nigeria. *Management Dynamics in the Knowledge economy* 7(3), 291-306.
- Omoke, V. Aturu, A. C. Nwaogbe, O. R. Ajiboye, A. O. & Diugwu, I. (2018). *Analysis of the Impact of Port Operations on Nigerian Economy: A Focus on Apapa Seaport*. *Nigeria University of Minna*.
- Onuorah, A.C. (2018). Trade liberalization and Economic Growth in Nigeria. *International Journal Advanced Research*. 6 (9) 389-400.
- Onyeabor, E.U. (2018). *Appraisal of the Importance of Maritime Transportation to Nigeria's Economy*. Paper Presented at the *National Summit of the Maritime Sector Held on 11th – 13th September 2018 at Rockview Hotel Royale Abuja*.
- Osabohien, R. Akinpelumi D. Mathew O. Okafor V. Iku E. Olawande T. & Okorie U. (2019). Agricultural exports and economic Growth in Nigeria: An Econometric Analysis. IOP conf. series. *Earth and environmental Science* 331.
- Osidipe, O.A. Onuchukwu O. Otto G. & Neribee S.G. (2018). Trade Liberalization and selected manufacturing sectoral Groups in Nigeria. *World Journal of Innovative Research*. 5 (60) 37-46.
- Park, N.G. & Suh S.C. (2019). Tendency toward mega containerships and the constraints of container terminals. *Journal of Maritime Science and Engineering* 7 131.
- Premathilaka, W.H.V. (2018). Determining the factors affecting the turnaround time of container vessels: a case study on Port of Colombo. *World Maritime University Dissertations*. 600.
- Proshare, (2020). *Nigeria Maritime Industry*. <https://www.proshareng.com/news/transportation/Nigeria-Maritime-Industry/43571#>.
- Rodrigue, J. & Notteboom T. (2020). *The Geography of Transport Systems*. *New York: Routledge*.
- Saeed, N. Cullinane K. & Sødal S. (2021). Exploring the relationships between maritime connectivity international trade and domestic production. *Maritime Policy & Management* 48(4) 497–511 <https://doi.org/10.1080/03088839.2020.1802783>.
- Sanyal, K. & Jones R. (1982). The theory of trade in middle products. *American Economic Review* 72(1) 16-31.
- Somuyiwa, A.O. & Ogundele, A.V. (2015). Correlate of port cargo dwell time components in Tin-Can Reach Stackers system Apapa Lagos. *European Journal of Logistics Purchasing and Supply Chain Management* 3(1) 44-57.
- Stopford, M. (2009). *Maritime Economics* 3rd Edition. *New York: McGraw Hill International*
- UNCTAD, (2018). African Continental Free Trade Area: Challenges and opportunities of tariff reductions. *UNCTAD Research Paper*. 15.
- UNCTAD. (2019). *Economic Development in Africa Report 2019: Made in Africa: Rules of Origin for Enhanced Intra-African Trade* <https://unctad.org/pressmaterial/facts-figures>.
- UNCTAD, (2021). Review of Maritime Transport 2021 (Review of Maritime Transport). https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/rmt2021_en_0.pdf.
- UNCTAD, (2022). Review of Maritime trade among Nations https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/rmt2018ch4_en.pdf.
- UNCTAD, (2023). Review of Maritime trade review of countries https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/rmt2023_ch7_en.
- Yakubu, M. & Akanegbu, B.N. (2018). Trade Openness and economic Growth: Evidence from Nigeria. *European Journal of Business economics and Accountancy*. 6 4.